

THE LONG-TERM TREND IN GLOBAL WARMING AND ITS CAUSE IS UNIFORM ACCELERATION SINCE 1980

by
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Abstract.

In this project, we shall discover, through my series of graphs, that, this series of four publicly accessible data, for four key metrics for Global Warming, have all been in uniform acceleration since 1980, and are all causally related:

(1) Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al, in the Global Carbon Budget, measure:

The annual magnitude of our world carbon dioxide emissions, and the annual magnitude of increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide, from which we derive, annually cumulative world carbon dioxide emissions, and annually cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide.

<https://globalcarbonbudget.org>

<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-659>

(2) Dr Xin Lan et al, in the NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory, measure:

Annually cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide, from which we derive, the annual change in atmospheric carbon dioxide.

<https://gml.noaa.gov/about/aboutgml.html>

<https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends>

(3) Dr Norman Loeb et al, in the NASA CERES Team, measure:

The Earth's top of the atmosphere fluxes, from which we derive, the Earth's net heating flux, Earth's annual radiant heat energy absorption, and Earth's cumulative radiant heat energy absorption anomaly.

<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people/dr-norman-loeb>

(4) Dr Colin Morice et al, in the Met Office Hadley Centre, measure:

Global Mean Surface Temperature, HadCRUT5, from which we derive, the annual change in Global Mean Surface Temperature.

<https://weather.metoffice.gov.uk/climate/met-office-hadley-centre/index>

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadcrut5>

Plain Language Summary.

We may understand, that normally,
Global Warming and Climate Change, are conflated into only Climate Change,
and our news services ask “Was this extreme weather caused by Climate Change ?”
No, Climate Change is not a cause, Climate Change is an effect, caused by Global Warming,
and this extreme weather was an expression of Climate Change.
Global Warming has a definite cause and definite metrics,
whereas, Climate Change is statistical and may be attributed to its cause, Global Warming.

We may understand, there is this whole sequence of causes and effects,
which are normally summarised as, anthropogenic climate change:

The huge annually incremental magnitude,
of our world population demand, for carbon combustion energy, causes:

The huge annually incremental magnitude,
of our world carbon combustion energy economy, which causes:

The huge annually incremental magnitude,
of our world carbon dioxide emissions, into, our finite air atmosphere, which causes:

The uniform acceleration,
of accumulating carbon dioxide, in, our finite air atmosphere, which causes:

The distressing annual intensification of the greenhouse effect, which causes:

The distressing uniform acceleration,
of our Earth’s cumulative absorption of radiant heat energy from the Sun,
which is what Global Warming is, which causes:

The distressing uniform acceleration,
in our Global Mean Surface Temperature, GMST,
which is what, we, our whole world population, know as Global Warming,
and which is the temperature by which 1.5°C Global Warming is measured by,
which causes:

Global oceans warming, global oceans de-oxygenation, global oceans acidification,
global sea levels rising, global ice melting, global snowpack melting,
the intensification of tropical cyclones and wind and rain storms, coastal flooding and rain flooding,
over-hot sunny summer days and heatwaves, heat related deaths and wildfires,
which are all distressing to all life on Earth, including all human life,
which is what, we, our whole world population, know as Climate Change.

Therefore, we, our whole world population,
really need to care, and really need to choose,
to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy,
every day, now and forevermore, please.

Therefore, all our world's climate scientists,
in the IPCC, and all their Member Governments,
the WMO, NASA and NOAA, the Met Office, and all our COP Climate Conferences,
really need to start asking us, our whole world population,
in all our world's news services:

“Please can we, our whole world population,
please really care, and please really choose,
to us, less or much less, carbon combustion energy,
every day, now and forevermore, please !”

Method.

We shall see in this project, that I have had this unique and novel mathematical insight, with which, I have created this series of graphs, in my series of LibreOffice Calc spreadsheets, using this elegant mathematical technique:

(1) For each of the four sets of Global Warming data, I have created, the data and the graph, for the annual change of these four metrics, which illustrate, natural variation with an amplitude, with a gentle increasing trend, in these four metrics.

(2) I then applied simple linear regression, SLR, to the annual change of these four metrics, in order to reveal the average linear increasing trend in these data.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simple_linear_regression

The formula that I used for simple linear regression is:

$$y = mx + c$$

$$S_{xy} = (\text{Sum } X_i Y_i) - (\text{Sum } X_i)(\text{Sum } Y_i)/n$$

$$S_{xx} = (\text{Sum } X_i X_i) - (\text{Sum } X_i)(\text{Sum } X_i)/n$$

$$m = S_{xy} / S_{xx}$$

$$c = (\text{Sum } Y_i)/n - m * (\text{Sum } X_i)/n$$

Where:

X_i = the time values for the data, eg, whole years, or decimal time.

Y_i = the Global Warming data.

n = the number of data items.

(3) We can see, that, the annual change metric, is metric per time, so, this is analogous to velocity, v . Therefore, I compared the resulting SLR equation, $y = mx + c$, to the analogous equation of motion, $v = u + at$. This means, that the gradient in the SLR, is equivalent to acceleration, a , which is what we want to identify.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Equations_of_motion

(4) Then, for each of the four sets of Global Warming data, I created, the data and the graph, for the summation of the annual change metrics, so, this summation, is the total metric over time.

We can see, that the annual change metric, is the time-derivative, of the total metric, and, the total metric, is the time-integral, of the annual change metric. Understanding this relationship is key to understanding, the analogy with the equations of motion, and how we identify that Global Warming is in uniform acceleration.

(5) Similarly, the SLR of the quantity per time, which is equivalent to the equation of motion, $v = u + at$, is a time-derivative. Therefore, I time-integrated the SLR equation of motion to obtain quantity, equivalent to position: $v = ds/dt$, therefore, $s = \int (v) dt = \int (u + at) dt = s_0 + ut + at^2/2$. This equation is a quadratic, which is analogous to uniform acceleration.

(5) I compared this time-integral to the annually cumulative metric, for each of the four data sets.

Where:

s = position = quantity.

v = velocity = rate of change of quantity.

a = acceleration = rate of change of rate of change of quantity.

t = decimal time in years.

Significantly, each simple linear regression equation, and each time-integral, and all their constants, and all their scalar dimensions units, are consistent and resolve correctly.

Part One. The Global Carbon Budget.

Our World Carbon Dioxide Emissions into Our Finite Air Atmosphere.

In their Global Carbon Budget, Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS et al, measure:

<https://globalcarbonbudget.org>

- (1) The annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy.
- (2) The annual magnitude of carbon dioxide that remains in our atmosphere.
- (3) The annual magnitude of carbon dioxide that gets absorbed by our oceans, which is cause global oceans' acidification.
- (4) The annual magnitude of carbon dioxide, that is absorbed by our whole Earths' green plant photosynthesis.

On Tuesday 11 November 2025,
Professor Pierre Friedlingstein FRS spoke with Professor Jim Al-Khalili CBE FRS,
on his BBC Radio 4 'Life Scientific' programme,

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/m002m031>,

where Pierre explained, that, of the total world carbon dioxide emissions,
about one half remain and accumulate in the atmosphere,
and about one quarter are absorbed in our oceans,
and about one quarter are absorbed by all green plant photosynthesis.

Figure 1, illustrates these four annual magnitudes,
along with each of their simple linear regressions, SLRs, which do illustrate linear increasing trends.
It is important to recognise, that these are, annual magnitudes,
which are, magnitudes per year, so that, in comparison to the equations for motion,
these magnitudes per year, are analogous to velocity.

And, in the equations for motion, a linear increasing trend in velocity, means, uniform acceleration.
Such that: $v = u + at$, where, v = the magnitude per year, u = the initial value, when $t=0$,
 a = the uniform acceleration, and t = decimal time in years.

Figure 1.

Annual World Carbon Dioxide Magnitudes (GtCO₂/y) (1960-2024)

Professor Pierre Friedlingstein et al

<https://globalcarbonbudget.org>

<https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-659>

For Figure 2:

(1) I sum the four annual magnitudes, to illustrate their four cumulative magnitudes.

(2) I time-integrate, the four SLR equations for magnitudes per year, to obtain, magnitudes.

Such that: $s = \int (u + at) dt = s_0 + ut + at^2/2$,

where, s = the magnitude, s_0 = the initial magnitude, when $t=0$,

and this equation is a quadratic curve that illustrates uniform acceleration.

Figure 2, clearly illustrates,

that the cumulative magnitude of world carbon dioxide emissions,

and accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, do closely approximate to uniform acceleration.

The key insight is to recognise, that linear annual incremental,

world carbon dioxide emissions, into, our finite air atmosphere, illustrated in Figure 1,

directly causes, the uniform acceleration of accumulating carbon dioxide,

in, our finite air atmosphere, illustrated in Figure 2.

I believe that I may be the first person to make this observation,

from Professor Pierre Friedlingstein's data,

that accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide is in uniform acceleration since 1960.

Therefore, we can quantify the uniform acceleration of accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide as:

Time-integral SLR CO₂ = (5.5295 GtCO₂) + (5.3693 GtCO₂/y) * t + (0.2299 GtCO₂/y/y) * t² / 2

Where, t = decimal time in years since 1960.

Therefore, accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide is accelerating at 0.2299 GtCO₂/y/y.

This acceleration of 0.2299 GtCO₂/y/y may not seem like very much,

but this quantity is enough to account for the uniform acceleration in accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, over the last sixty years since 1960.

Figure 2.

Cumulative World Carbon Dioxide Magnitudes (GtCO₂) (1960-2024)

Professor Pierre Friedlingstein et al

<https://globalcarbonbudget.org>

<https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-659>

[Part Two. The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory. Accumulating Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide.](#)

The NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory, have been measuring, monthly, the magnitude of accumulating global atmospheric carbon dioxide, at their Mauna Loa Observatory, since 1959. Dr. Xin Lan and Dr Pieter Tans, of NOAA/GML, and Dr. Ralph Keeling, of The Scripps Institution of Oceanography.
<https://gml.noaa.gov/about/stafflist.html>
<https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends>

For Figure 3, I calculated the annual averages, from the monthly data, then I calculated the difference between the annual averages, to obtain magnitude of change per year, which we can see, has a natural variability, with an amplitude, and a gently increasing trend.

Then, I calculated the simple linear regression, SLR, of this data. This SLR is analogous to the equation of motion: $v = u + at$.

This simple linear regression does illustrate a long-term trend, in increasing magnitude in the annual magnitudes of change per year.

If we look at the NOAA graph for annual increase in CO₂ at Mauna Loa, on their webpage:
<https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/gr.html>

then we can see for their analysis, they have measured decadal averages, which do illustrate a multi-decadal increasing trend, however, it appears, that NOAA may have not yet applied simple linear regression to their whole data set.

I believe that I may be the first person to have had this insight, and to have carried out this analysis, of applying simple linear regression to the annual increase in CO₂ at Mauna Loa.

Figure 3.

NOAA GML Mauna Loa - Annual Increment in Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide (ppm/y) (1960-2025)

Dr Xin Lan - NOAA GML (gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends)

Dr Ralph Keeling - Scripps Institution of Oceanography (scrippsco2.ucsd.edu)

https://gml.noaa.gov/webdata/ccgg/trends/co2/co2_gr_mlo.csv

Figure 4, illustrates the Keeling Curve.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Keeling_Curve

For Figure 4, I illustrate the NOAA data for accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, along with the time-integral of the SLR which is a quadratic curve, which illustrates uniform acceleration, which does approximate closely to the NOAA data.

This time-integral of the SLR is analogous to the equation of motion:

$$s = s_0 + ut + at^2/2.$$

Figure 4, which illustrates, accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, and its SLR time-integral quadratic curve, directly corresponds with the key insight in Part One, that linear annual incremental world carbon dioxide emissions, into, our finite air atmosphere, Figure 1, directly causes, the uniform acceleration of accumulating carbon dioxide, in, our finite air atmosphere, Figure 2.

I believe, that I may be the first person to make the observation, that accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide in the Keeling Curve, does approximate to uniform acceleration since at least 1960.

From figure 4 we can measure the accumulation of atmospheric carbon dioxide as:

$$\text{Time-integral SLR CO}_2 = (312.500 \text{ ppm}) + (0.756757 \text{ ppm/y}) * t + (0.028897 \text{ ppm/y/y}) * t^2 / 2$$

Where, t is decimal time in years since 1960.

Therefore, accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide is accelerating at 0.028897 ppm/y/y.

This acceleration of 0.028897 ppm/y/y may not seem like very much,

but this quantity is enough to account for the uniform acceleration in accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, over the last sixty years since 1960.

Figure 4.

NOAA GML - The Keeling Curve - Accumulating Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide (ppm) (1960-2025)

Dr Xin Lan - NOAA GML (gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends)

Dr Ralph Keeling - Scripps Institution of Oceanography (scrippsco2.ucsd.edu)

https://gml.noaa.gov/webdata/ccgg/trends/co2/co2_mm_mlo.csv

Part Three. NASA CERES. Understanding the Top of the Atmosphere Heating and Cooling Fluxes.

Our Planet Earth receives Radiant Energy – Heat and Light – from our Sun of our Solar System.

Our Sun of our Solar System radiates energy – heat and light – in all directions into space.
Our planet Earth orbits our Sun every year.

Our planet Earth receives radiant visible light,
and shortwave infrared, SWIR, radiant heat energy from the Sun.
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shortwave_radiation_\(optics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shortwave_radiation_(optics))
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infrared>

A proportion of this SWIR radiant heat energy is reflected back into space,
and a proportion is absorbed by the Earth's land and seas and oceans.

A proportion of the SWIR radiant heat energy, that is absorbed by the Earth's land and seas and oceans,
is re-radiated back into the atmosphere, as longwave infrared, LWIR, radiant heat energy.
A proportion of this LWIR is radiated back into space.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outgoing_longwave_radiation

A proportion of this LWIR is absorbed, by accumulating greenhouse gas molecules,
primarily, accumulating carbon dioxide, in the atmosphere,
this is the annually incremental Greenhouse Effect, and this is the origin of Global Warming.

Warmed greenhouse gas molecules in the atmosphere,
then re-radiate this LWIR back to the Earth,
causing, the land and seas and oceans temperatures to rise,
as well as, over-hot sunny days and heatwaves and heat domes,
which is what we, our world population, know as Global Warming.

The Earth's Energy Budget.

In The USA, NASA, is their National Aeronautics and Space Administration. NASA have established their series of very important Earth Observation Satellites. NASA have their CERES (Clouds and Earth Radiant Energy System) Measurements Satellites.

With CERES, NASA Scientists, led by their Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb, <https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people> are able to measure the Top of the Atmosphere (TOA) heating and cooling fluxes, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radiative_flux that govern the Earth's Energy Budget:

(1) Total Solar Irradiance, TSI, is a heating flux.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solar_irradiance

(2) Top of the Atmosphere, TOA, Outgoing Shortwave Infrared Radiant Heat Energy, OSWIR, is a cooling flux.

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shortwave_radiation_\(optics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shortwave_radiation_(optics))

(3) Top of the Atmosphere, TOA, Outgoing Longwave Infrared Radiant Heat Energy, OLWIR, is a cooling flux.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outgoing_longwave_radiation

(4) The Earth's Energy Imbalance, EEI, is The Net Heating Flux, $NHF = TSI/4 - (OSWIR + OLWIR)$.

The Net Heating Flux into the whole Earth System is what, Global Warming is.

Figure 5, illustrates the Earth's Energy Budget.

Citation: Professor Piers Forster et al (2021).

Chapter 7, The Earth's Energy Budget, Figure 7.2.

Working Group I. The Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) of the IPCC.

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures/chapter-7/figure-7-2>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>

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Figure 5. IPCC AR6 Chapter 7. The Earth's Energy Budget.

From Figure 5, we can see, the Top of the Atmosphere fluxes are:

- | | |
|--|--|
| (1) TSI/4 \approx 340 W/m ² | The Sun's whole heating flux. |
| (2) OSWIR \approx 100 W/m ² | The Earth's reflected cooling flux. |
| (3) OLWIR \approx 239 W/m ² | The Earth's radiated cooling flux. |
| (4) NHF \approx 1 W/m ² | The Earth's net heating flux = The Earth's Energy Imbalance EEI. |

[NASA CERES TOA Fluxes' Data.](#)

(1) NASA CERES produce data for Total Solar Irradiance (TSI).

The value for TSI is for the whole Electromagnetic Spectrum, from Ultraviolet, to Visible, to Infrared.

<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/data/general-product-info>

https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/documents/TSIdata/CERES_EBAF_Ed2.8_DailyTSI.txt

This data, gives daily values, 1/1/2000 to 31/1/2026.

I put this data in my LibreOffice Calc spreadsheet,

and I processed this data, to produce monthly averages and annual averages.

(2) NASA Langley Atmospheric Science Data Center DAAC,

produce CERES Energy Balanced and Filled (EBAF) TOA Monthly means data, Edition4.2.1, in NetCDF (.nc),

for Outgoing Shortwave Infrared Radiant Heat Energy (OSWIR),

and for Outgoing Longwave Infrared Radiant Heat Energy (OLWIR):

<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/data/data-product-dois/>

https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/CERES/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1

The direct download NetCDF (.nc) file, for monthly data, from March 2000, to December 2025, is:
https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/data/CERES/EBAF/TOA_Edition4.2.1/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1_200003-202512.nc

I had to create a login account with NASA to be able to download this file.

I searched and learned, that NetCDF files can be viewed with NASA's Panoply software, which I have been able to download and install, and run and learn to use, on my Xubuntu Linux operating system.

<https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply>

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NetCDF>

With these data, for (1) TSI and (2) OSWIR and OLWIR, I have been able to create the following three graphs:

Figure 6, illustrates Total Solar Irradiance, which is the whole Earth's heating flux (Watts per metre squared) (W/m^2).

Figure 7, illustrates the Top of The Atmosphere, TSI/4 Heating Flux, and OSWIR and OLWIR Cooling Fluxes. We can see that the values for these TOA fluxes, in Figure 7, correspond well, with the Top of the Atmosphere values in Figure 5, the Earth's Energy Budget diagram.

Figure 8, Top of The Atmosphere Net Heating Flux, $NHF = TSI/4 - (OSWIR + OLWIR)$. We can see that the Net Heating Flux has quite a large natural variability, but it does have a gently increasing trend, which is illustrated by its simple linear regression.

In Figure 8, we can see that the Net Heating Flux annual averages, approximate well, with the value $1 W/m^2$ in the Earth's Energy Budget diagram.

Figure 6.

NASA CERES Total Solar Irradiance TSI Flux (W/m²) (2000-2025)
Principal Scientist Dr Normal Loeb (<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people>)
https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/documents/TSIdata/CERES_EBAF_Ed2.8_DailyTSI.txt

Figure 7.

NASA CERES Top of The Atmosphere Heating and Cooling Fluxes (W/m²) (2000-2025)

Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb (<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people>)
https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/CERES/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1

Figure 8.

NASA CERES Top of The Atmosphere TOA Net Heating Flux NHF (W/m²) (2000-2025)

Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb (<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people>)

https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/CERES/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1

- Monthly Average Net Heating Flux
- Annual Average Net Heating Flux
- Simple Linear Regression Monthly Average Flux = $(0.514264 \text{ W/m}^2) + (0.033521 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{y}) * t \mid t(0) = 1/1/2000 \mid [t] = y$
- Simple Linear Regression Annual Average Flux = $(0.382424 \text{ W/m}^2) + (0.042403 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{y}) * t \mid t(0) = 1/1/2000 \mid [t] = y$

For Figure 8, in LibreOffice Calc, I calculated:

- (1) The simple linear regression for the monthly values of the Net Heating Flux.
- (2) The annual averages for the Net Heating Flux, and the simple linear regression SLR of the annual averages, which indicates, that the Top of The Atmosphere Net Heating Flux, is gently increasing, with its SLR gradient of $0.042403 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{y}$.

The annually incremental annual average TOA Net Heating Flux, is the magnitude of the power (Watts/m^2), which is causing annually incremental Global Warming.

Climate Scientists could correctly define:

- (1) The Annual Intensity of The Greenhouse Effect, is, The Annual Average Net Heating Flux, for each year.
- (2) The Annual Intensification of The Greenhouse Effect, is, The rate of increase in the simple linear regression of the Annual Average NHF = $0.042403 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{y}$.

Then, to make Figures 9 and 10, I needed to time-integrate Figure 8, by translating, Irradiance and Radiance (Power), into Irradiation and Radiation (Energy), for the whole surface of the Earth.

Power (P) (Watts) (W) is the rate of Energy (E) (Joules) (J) per Time (t) (seconds) (s).

1 Watt = 1 Joule per 1 Second. $1 \text{ W} = 1 \text{ J/s}$

$$P = dE/dt$$

$$E = \int P dt$$

For instance.

Let us take the value, for TOA Net Heating Flux, that is heating the Earth = 1 W/m^2 .
Where, 1 W/m^2 , is per metre squared, for the whole surface area of the Earth,
not the cross-section area of the Earth.

The surface area of the Earth:

$$\begin{aligned} &= 4 * \text{Pi} * (6371 \text{ km})^2 \\ &= 510.064 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^2 = 510.064 \text{ Tm}^2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Total Net Power, that is heating the Earth:

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 \text{ W/m}^2) * (510.064 \text{ Tm}^2) \\ &= 510.064 \text{ TW}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Net Energy per day, that has heated the Earth:

$$\begin{aligned} &= (510.064 \text{ TJ/s}) * (60\text{s/m}*60\text{m/h}*24\text{h/d}) \\ &= 44.069570 \text{ EJ/d}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Net Energy per year that has heated the Earth:

$$\begin{aligned} &= (44.070 \text{ EJ/d}) * (365.256 \text{ d/y}) \\ &= 16.096675 \text{ ZJ/y}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, when Net Heating Flux averages 1 W/m^2 for one year,
the Earth absorbs 16.096675 Zetta Joules, of Radiant Heat Energy, in that year,
which is the magnitude of Global Warming for that one year.

Therefore, I have calculated the scalar dimensions units conversion factor,
for Net Heating Flux to Earth's Annual Radiant Heat Energy Absorption,
which is, literally, the Earth's Energy Imbalance.

$$\text{Annual Energy} = \text{Earth's Energy Imbalance} = \text{Annual Average Net Heating Flux} * (16.096675 \text{ ZJ/y}) / (\text{W/m}^2)$$

For Figure 9, in LibreOffice Calc, I calculated, the Annual Energy, the Earth's Energy Imbalance, for every value of Annual Average TOA Net Heating Flux, which is, the Earth's Annual Radiant Heat Energy Absorption, EARHEA, and, I calculated the simple linear regression SLR for this Annual Energy data.

When we compare Figure 8, Net Heating Flux, NHF, with Figure 9, Earth's Radiant Heat Energy Absorption, EARHEA, we can see, that the patterns, for the annual averages, and their simple linear regressions, are scale versions of each other, and are directly related, by the above conversion factor: $(16.096675 \text{ ZJ/y}) / (\text{W/m}^2)$.

For Figure 10, I then calculated, the progressive sum of the Monthly Energies, to illustrate Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Absorption Anomaly, ECRHEAA, and I time-integrated the simple linear regression to illustrate uniform acceleration.

Figure 10, illustrates, Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Absorption Anomaly ECRHEAA. ECRHEAA, is the accumulating heat energy of the whole Earth System, since 2000, this is what, Global Warming, is.

Figure 9.

NASA CERES Earth's Annual Radiant Heat Energy Absorption EARHEA (ZJ/y) (2000-2025)

Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb (<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people>)

https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/CERES/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1

Figure 10.

NASA CERES Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Absorption Anomaly ECRHEAA (ZJ) (2000-2025)

Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb (<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/people>)
https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/CERES/CERES_EBAF-TOA_Edition4.2.1

From Figure 10, we can see, from 1/1/2000 to 31/12/2025, the whole Earth System has absorbed, of the order of, 390 Zetta Joules, of heat energy.

From Figure 10, we can see, that the Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Absorption Anomaly, is accelerating at 0.682172 Zetta Joules per year per year, with the approximation, to uniform acceleration:

Time-integral SLR ECRHEAA = (2.764454 ZJ) + (6.160802 ZJ/y) * t + (0.682172 ZJ/y/y) * t² / 2
Where, t = decimal time since 2000.

This equation is the time integral, of the simple linear regression, for Earth's Annual Radiant Heat Energy Absorption EARHEA, in Figure 9, which is the quantity of radiant heat energy that the Earth has absorbed each year:

SLR EARHEA = (6.160802 ZJ/y) + (0.682172 ZJ/y/y) * t
Where, t = decimal time since 2000.

I believe I may be the first person to make the observation, that Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Absorption, is in uniform acceleration since at least 2000.

In September 2025, I was actually inspired to create this whole project and carry out this whole analysis, when I had searched and found this original graph by NASA CERES Principal Scientist Dr Norman Loeb:

Earth's Radiation Balance, 2000-2023.

<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/5173>

When I saw this graph, I just thought, this is, what Global Warming is, and this curve has to be acceleration, and I must prove it.

[Comparison with IPCC AR6 Chapter 7.](https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/chapter/chapter-7)

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/chapter/chapter-7>

Executive Summary. Earth's Energy Budget.

“The global energy inventory increased by, 282 [177 to 387] Zetta Joules (ZJ) for the period 1971–2006, and **152 ZJ** [100 to 205 ZJ] for the period 2006–2018.”

“This corresponds to an Earth energy imbalance, of 0.50 [0.32 to 0.69] W/m² for the period 1971–2006, increasing to **0.79 W/m²** [0.52 to 1.06 W/m²] for the period 2006–2018, expressed per unit area of Earth's surface.”

Citation: Professor Piers Forster et al (2021). Chapter 7, The Earth's Energy Budget. Working Group I. The Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) of the IPCC.

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures/chapter-7/>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>

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My Results.

Time Frame	Earth's Cumulative Radiant Heat Energy Anomaly	Earth's Energy Imbalance Net Heating Flux
1/1/2006	50.993 ZJ	0.637 W/m ²
1/1/2018	217.827 ZJ	1.146 W/m ²
Difference >>	166.834 ZJ	Average >> 0.891 W/m²

My results do compare reasonably well with the IPCC figures.

However, at their time of writing, IPCC Climate Scientists, did not appear to appreciate, that what they call the Earth's Energy Imbalance, being synonymous with, Net Heating Flux, has a continuous linear annually increasing trend, which I have illustrated in Figures 8 and 9, which may be described as, the annual intensification of the greenhouse effect.

[Part Four. The Met Office Hadley Centre. HadCRUT5 Global Mean Surface Temperature.](#)

The Met Office Hadley Centre HadCRUT5,
is their annual record for Global Mean Surface Temperature, GMST, since 1850.

<https://weather.metoffice.gov.uk/climate/met-office-hadley-centre/index>

<https://hadleyserver.metoffice.gov.uk/hadcrut5>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Global_surface_temperature

Citation. Dr Colin Morice et al. (2021).

An updated assessment of near-surface temperature change from 1850:
the HadCRUT5 data set. Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD032361>

The 1.5°C temperature limit for Global Warming,
which was enshrined by the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference,
is measured relative to the Pre-Industrial Average between 1850 and 1900.

As provided, the HadCRUT5 anomalies,
are calculated relative to the 1961–90 reference period.

On HadCRUT5, the Pre-Industrial 1850–1900 average temperature = -0.357361 °C.

Therefore, to obtain the level of warming, since the pre-industrial 1850–1900 period,
I needed to subtract -0.357361 °C from the HadCRUT5 temperature record.

For Figure 11, I calculated the annual differences in temperature, and I calculated their simple linear regression since 1980, which does illustrate a gently increasing gradient of $0.000456 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{y}/\text{y}$.

For Figure 12, I plotted HadCRUT5, adjusted to be relative to the Pre-Industrial Temperature, which does illustrate, that 2024 was the warmest year on record, when the temperature did go above $1.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ Global Warming, and the temperature was $1.526486 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, and I plotted the time-integral of the simple linear regression, which does illustrate, that the long-term trend in GMST Global Warming, is uniform acceleration since 1980.

From Figure 12, we can see that this tiny quantity, $0.000456 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{y}/\text{y}$, accounts for the uniform acceleration, in HadCRUT5 Global Mean Surface Temperature since 1980.

I believe that I may be the first person, to compare the HadCRUT5 GMST record since 1980, to uniform acceleration, by applying the time-integral of the simple linear regression of the annual changes in temperature.

Conclusion.

From my whole series of graphs, we may deduce, that, the observed uniform acceleration in accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, in Figures 1 & 2 & 3 & 4, causes, the observed uniform acceleration in Global Warming, in Figures 9 & 10 & 11 & 12.

I believe that I may be the first person, to have had this unique and novel insight, and do this analysis, using this elegant mathematical technique, of applying, and time-integrating, simple linear regression, to these four key Global Warming datasets, as described in my abstract, in order to illustrate that, Global Warming and its cause are in uniform acceleration since 1980, otherwise this knowledge would be normal and accepted by now, yet, it isn't, yet.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scientific_priority

Figure 11.

Met Office Hadley Centre - Annual Change in Global Mean Surface Temperature GMST (°C/y) (1980-2025)

Dr Colin Morice et al - The HadCRUT5 Data Set

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadcrut5>

Figure 12.

Met Office Hadley Centre HadCRUT5 Global Mean Surface Temperature (°C) (1960-2025)

Dr Colin Morice et al - The HadCRUT5 Data Set

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadcrut5>

Part Five. The True Need for True World Population Climate Action.

In reverse chronological order:

(1) 23 March 2026. WMO State of the Climate 2025 Report.

<https://wmo.int/publication-series/state-of-global-climate/state-of-global-climate-2025>

(2) 16 March 2026. BBC Radio 4 Inside Science. Is the Earth warming faster than we expected ?

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/w3ct8ty3>

Presenter Tom Whipple and Professor Laura Wilcox, helpfully discuss Dr Grant Foster and Professor Stefan Rahmsdorf's article, of 6 March 2026, listed in (3) below.

(3) 6 March 2026. Dr Grant Foster and Professor Stefan Rahmsdorf.

Global Warming Has Accelerated Significantly.

<https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2025GL118804>

This important article makes quite a complex analysis, that reveals that Global Warming is accelerating.

My project, here, is intended to independently compliment and contribute to, Dr Grant Foster's and Professor Stefan Rahmsdorf's research.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stefan_Rahmstorf

(4) 4 February 2026, in this important Met Office News Article:

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/climate/seasonal-to-decadal/seasonal-forecast/forecasts/co2-forecast>

Professor Richard Betts MBE FRMetS et al,

in their Mauna Loa carbon dioxide forecast for 2026, state,

world carbon dioxide emissions, & therefore cumulative atmospheric carbon dioxide, continue to grow too fast to comply with IPCC requirements for 2026.

The problem is, in this article, Professor Richard Betts illustrates, the optimistic need for the increasing curve, in accumulating atmospheric carbon dioxide, Figure 4, to begin to level off, well, this just isn't happening.

Why ? Because, we, the world population, are not caring to reduce our demand for carbon combustion energy. For the last eleven years, ever since the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference, we, our whole world population, have been frequently told by climate scientists in our news services, that “we need to reduce our carbon dioxide emissions”, clearly, we, our whole world population, just aren’t doing this.

(4) 10 November 2025, at 1m 36s, into this YouTube video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WzCIHA8TiHI>

IPCC Chair Professor Sir Jim Skea CBE FRSE, says:

“Based on the evidence of the most recent IPCC reports, it is now almost inevitable that 1.5 degrees Celsius of global warming, will be exceeded in the near term. This is unambiguously due to insufficient climate action, over the last few years, and the consequent, continued increase in greenhouse gas emissions. But, returning global warming to 1.5 degrees Celsius, by the end of this century may still be possible. It would involve, immediate, deep, and sustained, reductions, in carbon dioxide emissions.”

In my plain language summary, we have read, that, the huge annual magnitude of our world population demand for carbon energy, causes, the huge annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy, which causes, the huge annual magnitude, of our world carbon dioxide emissions, into our finite air atmosphere.

The problem is, Professor Sir Jim Skea, is actually assiduously avoiding saying:

(I) That, immediate deep sustained reductions in carbon dioxide emissions, can logically only happen, by reducing the annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy, which is measured by, Professor Pierre Friedlingstein et al in their Global Carbon Budget.

(II) That (I) can be helped, by us, our whole world population, actually caring and actually choosing to reduce our demand for carbon energy, by moderating our lifestyles, by our own freedom of choice, this is not something that can be legislated for, but this can be asked for.

The IPCC official approach is, carbon dioxide emissions are only to be reduced, by the Nationally Determined Contributions, NDCs, of all IPCC Member Governments, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nationally_determined_contribution which includes decarbonisation, which is what mitigation is understood to mean, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Climate_change_mitigation https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fossil_fuel_phase-out and in no way, are we, the whole world population, nor, are we, all the IPCC Member Governments' countries' populations, asked to care, and choose to reduce our demand for carbon energy, by our own freedom of choice, in order to help to reduce the annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy. This logic has never been expressed.

(5) 23 September 2025. Michael Jenkins. The discovery that global warming is accelerating. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183234>

This was my first project to independently illustrate, that Global Warming and its cause are in uniform acceleration. This project, now, is my complete rethink and rewrite of this original project.

(6) 24 February 2025, at 1m 16s, into this YouTube video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V165ZAraY8Q>

UNEP Executive Director Inger Anderson, says:

“The IPCC through this (7th Assessment Report) cycle will provide the science, that backs nations in implementing the national climate plans, the NDCs, that they are updating this year. These plans must be stronger, and collectively promised, to almost halve greenhouse gas emission by 2030, for a long term 1.5 degrees Celsius trajectory.”

(7) 26 July 2021, similarly, at At 3m 8s into this YouTube video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5FCPLIF6P4g>

**Prior to COP26, the appointed COP26 President Alok Sharma, says:
"To keep the 1.5 degree limit alive, we've got to halve global emissions by 2030."**

(8) 4 April 2022: IPCC. **“The evidence is clear: the time for action is now. We can halve emissions by 2030.”**
<https://www.ipcc.ch/2022/04/04/ipcc-ar6-wgiii-pressrelease>

“In the scenarios we assessed, limiting warming to around 1.5°C, requires global greenhouse gas emissions to peak before 2025 at the latest, and be reduced by 43% by 2030.”

(9) United Nations: Net Zero.
<https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/net-zero-coalition>

“To keep global warming to no more than 1.5°C, as called for in the Paris Agreement, emissions need to be reduced by 45% by 2030, and reach net zero by 2050.

In (6)(7)(8)(9), we have read, that to keep global warming below 1.5°C, it has been the official science-led goal, since the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference, that the need is, to reduce world annual carbon dioxide emissions by almost half by 2030.

Figure 1, illustrates world annual carbon dioxide emissions, now, is 2026, eleven years since the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference, clearly, world annual carbon dioxide emissions, are not even beginning to reduce, let alone halve by 2030.

Logically, halving world annual carbon dioxide emissions, can only happen, by halving the annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy.

And, halving the annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy, can be helped, by us, our whole world population, actually caring, and actually choosing, to reduce our demand for carbon energy, by moderating our lifestyles, by our own freedom of choice, this is not something that can be legislated for, but this is something that can be asked for.

Yet, this logic has never been stated, to us, our world population, in our world news services.

The IPCC do work with all their Member Governments, to implement all their Member Governments’ Nationally Determined Contributions, NDCs, for national carbon dioxide reductions.

However, all this work, to create Nationally Determined Contributions, is done without the inclusion and co-operation, of all the IPCC's Member Governments' countries' news services and populations.

I have been listening to BBC Radio 4, at least since the time of the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference.

Listening to BBC Radio 4, for all these years, I have observed, that, yes, the reality of Global Warming and Climate Change & the need to reduce carbon dioxide emissions are accepted, however, no, all BBC Radio 4 journalists, and all climate scientists, and all politicians, who ever speak about Climate Change, to us, our UK Population, on BBC Radio 4, are all actually in denial, and, they all actually always assiduously avoid, ever having to say, that logically, reducing our world annual carbon dioxide emissions, can only happen, by reducing the annual magnitude of our world carbon energy economy, and that, this can be helped, by the now ineluctable need, for us, our whole world population, to actually care, and actually choose, to reduce our world population demand, for carbon energy, by moderating our lifestyles, by our own freedom of choice, and that, our news services can ask us to please do this.

People keep saying in our news services, we must act on climate, there needs to be more climate action, however, ironically, we, our whole world population, actually need, to act less, and do less, with carbon energy. As a world population, we need to learn, to be more content and appreciative, with what we have, and where we live, and, we need to learn, to moderate our lifestyles, and to freely choose to use less carbon energy.

Okay, so eleven years, since the Paris 2015 COP21 Climate Conference, of us, our world population, caring, and choosing to reduce our demand for carbon energy may have been lost, however, Net Zero 2050, is still 24 years into the future, therefore, I believe, in a new way, from this time forth, that the IPCC Chair Professor Sir Jim Skea CBE FRSE, needs to make it their IPCC policy, to direct all their IPCC Member Governments to make it their policy, and direct all our world's climate scientists to make it their policy, to all work together inclusively, to encourage and inspire, us, all our world's countries' news services and populations, to really care, and really choose, to use, less or much less, carbon energy, by simply fairly asking, us, our whole world population, in all our world and national news services:

For World Population Climate Action,

The IPCC, and all their member governments, and all our world's climate scientists,
need to fairly ask us, our whole world population, in our whole world's news services,
and in each of our world's countries' news services, in each of our world's countries' languages:

**“Please can we, our whole population of our whole world,
please really care, and please really choose,
to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy,
every day, now and forevermore, please !”**

IPCC UNFCCC COP31+ WMO UNEP UN
NOAA NASA Met Office Royal Meteorological Society EU Copernicus

Figure 13.

This Scale Diagram, illustrates, that, Our Finite Air Atmosphere, is only a very delicate membrane, upon the entire surface, of Our Original Perfect, Beautiful Peaceful Planet Earth.

The above reason, is why, our finite air atmosphere, is being adversely affected, by the distressingly huge annual magnitude, of our world carbon dioxide emissions, which are caused by, the distressingly huge annual magnitude, of, our world population demand for carbon combustion energy.

The inner blue circle:
= the diameter of our planet earth = 12,742 kilometres.

The 1st inner red circle:
= 99% of the mass of our atmosphere
= 30 kilometres from the surface of our Earth.

The 2nd outer red circle:
= 99.99% of the mass of our atmosphere = Karman Line
= 100 kilometres from the surface of our Earth.

The IPCC, all their Member Governments, the WMO, NASA, NOAA, the Met Office, the Royal Meteorological Society, EU Copernicus, and all our World's Climate Scientists, have the right, to ask us, our whole world population, in all our whole world's news services:

“Please can we, our whole world population, please really care, and please really choose, to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy, every day, now and forevermore, please.”

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